

DOI

SKŁADNIKI KOMPETENCJI PŁCIOWEJ NADAWCÓW USŁUG SPOŁECZNYCH

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Streszczenie. We współczesnych procesach integracji europejskiej zakłada się potrzebę zapewnienia równości płci w naszym społeczeństwie, co wymaga nowego światopoglądu, zgodnie z którym stereotypowe postrzeganie kobiet i mężczyzn powinno zostać zastąpione ideą rozwijania ich osobowego potencjału. Kompetencje płciowe są postrzegane jako zdolność i gotowość do interakcji z ludźmi różnych płci na zasadach równości płci i zapośredniczone przez indywidualne psychologiczne charakterystyki płciowe, które przejawiają się w życiu codziennym, komunikacji i zachowaniu z osobami różnych płci.

Wyróżniają się takie podstawowe składniki kompetencji płciowej jak komponent treści (znajomość różnych zagadnień pedagogiki i psychologii płciowej), komponent refleksyjny (osobiste podejście do różnych problemów płciowych), komponent organizacyjny (umiejętność zarządzania procesem socjalizacji płciowej).

Słowa kluczowe: kompetencje, kompetencje płciowe, nadawca usług społecznych, składniki, struktura, specjalista społeczny.

COMPONENTS OF GENDER COMPETENCE OF SOCIAL SERVICE PROVIDERS

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Annotation. Modern European Integration Processes foresee necessity of providing gender equality in our society, which require new ideology, according to that the stereotypical perception of women and men should be replaced by the idea of developing their personal potential. Gender competence is considered as ability and readiness to interact with people of different sex on the basis of gender equality and also is mediate through individual-psychological gender characteristics, which manifest in daily life, in communication and behavior with persons of different sex. There are such basic components of gender competence as content component (knowledge of different questions of gender pedagogy and phycology), reflexive component (personal attitude to different gender issues), and organizational component (ability to manage the process of gender socialization).

Key words: Competence, gender competence, social service provider, components, social sphere specialist

СКЛАДОВІ ГЕНДЕРНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ НАДАВАЧІВ СОЦІАЛЬНИХ ПОСЛУГ

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Анотація. В сучасні євроінтеграційні процеси передбачають необхідність забезпечення гендерної рівності в нашому суспільстві, що вимагає нового світогляду, відповідно до якого стереотипне сприйняття жінок і чоловіків має бути замінено ідеєю розвитку їхнього особистісного потенціалу. Гендерна компетентність розглядається як здатність та готовність взаємодіяти з особами різної статі на засадах гендерної рівності та є опосередкованим через індивідуально-психологічні гендерні характеристики, які проявляються у повсякденному житті, спілкуванні та поведінці з особами різної статі.

Виділяють такі основні компоненти гендерної компетентності як змістовний компонент (знання різних питань гендерної педагогіки і психології), рефлексивний компонент (особистісне ставлення до різних гендерних проблем), організаційний компонент (вміння управляти процесом гендерної соціалізації).

Ключові слова: компетентність, гендерна компетентність, надавач соціальних послуг, компоненти, структура, фахівець соціальної сфери.

Setting the problem in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The process of gender competency formation of modern professionals is an urgent need that has arisen as a result of modern realities. Also, the process of gender competency formation will ensure success in further professional activity, interpersonal relationships, solving gender problematic situations, quality of social services, in self-development.

Modern European Integration Processes foresee necessity of providing gender equality in our society, which require new ideology, according to that the stereotypical perception of women and men should be replaced by the idea of developing their personal potential. Gender mainstreaming in all spheres of public life will provide a real opportunity for future professionals in the social sphere through a qualified understanding of its essence with respect to be treated as an equal disclosure by a person of his or her personal potential, and equal opportunity to realize it, regardless of gender.

The need to develop gender competence of specialists is declared by Law of Ukraine “To ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men”, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “To approve the State Social Programme on ensuring Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men for the period until 2016” (2012), Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine “Implementation of principals of gender equality in education” (Laws of Ukraine.2005)

The analysis of recent research and publications indicate that Ukrainian and Russian scientists, in particular. O. Voronina, I. Horoshko, I. Zerebkina, O. Zdravomyslova, O. Kikinedzi, V. Kravets, L. Popova, I. Tartakovska, H. Tomkina, indicate in their writings about the importance of gender component of the professional competence of specialists.

Goal and purposes of article – to analyze the essence of the concept “gender competence”, to determine structure, stages and components of forming gender competence of social sphere specialist; to determine level of gender competence of social sphere specialist.

Presenting main material .Gender competence is considered as ability and readiness to interact with persons of different sex on the basis of gender equality and is mediated through individual-psychological gender characteristics, which manifest themselves in everyday life, in communication and behavior with persons of different sex. I. Ivanova and B. Kravets emphasize the need of training personnel, who will have the methodology and technology of gender education and also the appropriate level of gender culture.

Considering in terms of pedagogical approach, according to I. Zagainova, the teacher’s gender competence is “the totality of the acquired knowledge about the essence of the gender approach in education, the ability to integrate a gender strategy into the organization of the pedagogical process and experience of using gender knowledge and skills as a basis for gender interaction in the educational system” (Zagainov. 2007.23)

Considering gender competence in accordance with the psychological approach, scientists make the following definitions: set of knowledge, skills, skills that cause interaction with persons of different sex on the basis of gender equality and are mediated through individual-psychological gender characteristics (masculinity / femininity, gender identity, gender role, gender attitudes and stereotypes) which appears in daily life, communication and behavior with persons of different sex” O. Nezhinskaya (*Nezhinskaya. 2008. 212-219*);” dynamic personality formation (student / specialist), including ideas about the appointment of men and women in society, peculiarities of masculine and feminine personality, the image of I, knowledge of the gender peculiarities of subjects of pedagogical influence; valuable attitude towards the representatives of different articles and their interaction” M. Radzivilova (*Radzivilova. 2009. 5*).

According to the sociological approach, from the point of view of the existing social inequality of men and women, I. Klyotsina considers gender competence as “a characteristic that allows a person not to be the subject or object of situations of gender inequality, but enables to notice these situations in his life; to resist sexism by discriminatory influence; do not create gender inequalities themselves” (*Klyotsina. 2007. 60-65*); T. Grabovskaya interprets it as “a process of directed and spontaneous influences on a person, which helps her to acquire knowledge about gender, norms, rules of behavior and guidelines according to cultural perceptions about the role, position and appointment of representatives of different sexes in society, promotes the formation of full members of public life and engages them to a well-established gender role system” (*Grabovskaya. 1999. 134*).

V. Vasilyeva also draws attention to the necessity of gender mainstreaming, since it will give a real opportunity for future specialists of the field of social services to respect both the equal disclosure by a person of his or her personal potential and the equal possibility of its realization, regardless of gender. (*Mishchik, Golovanova, Vasilyeva. 2006. 220*).

In the process of formation and development of gender competence of the personality of the social sphere specialist I. Klyotsina identifies three main stages of activity:

I. Stage - formation of gender knowledge as a stage of formation of the system of gender knowledge, which includes mastering basic ideas of gender theory to basic ideas of gender approach in modern practice.

II. Stage – forming the ability to analyze phenomena and situations of gender inequality - mastering the skills and analysis of one's own prejudices, research and analytics of personal behavior in which gender prejudices are manifested, as a process of awareness of situations where each individual is - an object or subject of demonstrating of gender prejudices.

The main task of this stage is learn to notice the manifestations of sexism and neo-sexism in their behavior, without allowing such manifestations in the management team, in education and in society.

III. Stage of developing skills of gender-competent behavior (*Klyotsina. 2007. 60-65*).

According to I. Muntyan, gender competence is a complex, structured professionally important neoplasm of personality, consisting of three components:

1) a content-based one that sets out and reflects the essence of conceptual frameworks in understanding the phenomena of gender and the gender approach in education;

2) operational-oriented, which focuses on the specific functions of professional activity related to gender education and education of the younger generation;

3) personally professional, which take cares of the area of expansion of the subjective space of the professional by overcoming his own gender stereotypes and awareness of his new potential possibilities of self-realization in all spheres of life

Klyotsina I.S. has explored the formation of gender competence in her writings. In her opinion, “Formation of gender competence is a purposeful activity, as a result of which person demonstrates competence in expressed gender component situations. In other words, it is a movement from gender incompetence to competence, that is, the acquisition and development of gender knowledge, skills and ways of gender correct behavior”. Selected components of gender competency (formulated as knowledge and skills) can help to formulate the final learning goals in the gender education process of public and municipal employees (*Klyotsina. 2007. 60-65*).

According to L. Stileva , the important component of gender competence of social care professional is “gender sensitivity – an ability to perceive, understand and model the impact of verbal, non-verbal, subjective influences of the social environment; methods and forms of providing social services, to the formation of gender identity of a person, the ability of a specialist to capture and respond to any manifestation of gender discrimination » (*Stileva. 2015*).

Kirilenko O.H proposes to define the gender competence of a specialist as "a component of professional competence, which allows to effectively perform professional activities on a gender basis" (*Kirilenko. 2012. 93-103*). Among the means of implementing this activity, he identified such skills. These include:

a) gnostic skills, namely, cognitive skills in the field of subject knowledge, which allow a positive attitude to gender theory; understand the changes that allow to be positive for gender theory; to understand the changes that are taking place in the gender sphere of modern society; analyze and understand the problems of gender socialization; to understand, analyze and evaluate gender stereotypes, roles, acts of behavior, and gender stereotypes, roles, acts of customer behavior; to realize personal meaning in gender self-education; to use the knowledge gained through the analysis of own activities and colleagues activities to improve own work;

b) designing skills that allow for the design of goals and objectives of the gender approach in professional activity; selection of technologies and methods for forming gender competence of social service providers;

c) constructive skills, the content of which is the selection and structuring of the content of education and upbringing; taking into account possible variants of change of course of educational and cognitive activity depending on their gender; constructing gender interaction with clients, colleagues, recipients of social services;

d) communicative skills that promote gender mainstreaming and communication; the ability to be creative in communicating and avoiding gender stereotypes and attitudes;

e) organizational skills that ensure the effective organization of professional activity in the context of taking into account the sexual characteristics of clients.

Gender competence is based on an analysis of models of gender relationships, which are evolving and changing in society. In the structure of gender competence of social service providers, can be distinguished cognitive, operational and personal components (pic.1).

Picture 1. Content and components of gender competence of social service providers (Nezhinskaya. 2008. 212-219)

Some scientists identify other components of gender competency formation. In particular, Danylenko L.I. identifies such components of gender competence:

1. The general cultural element includes knowledge of different peoples' models, understanding of the cultural conditionality of existing gender models, norms, stereotypes and attitudes;

2. The value element is related to the value orientations of professionals: knowledge, acceptance or rejection of such values as gender equality, gender tolerance, antisexism, that is orientation to patriarchal or egalitarian values

3. Educational cognitive element: ability to acquire knowledge on gender issues; the ability to critically analyze the gender patterns and models that are associated with society;

4. Information element: skills and abilities of free orientation in the information space, which touches on gender issue;

5. The communicative element includes the knowledge, skills and abilities needed for effective communication in the field of gender interaction, the skills of responsible self-representation

6. The social-labor element takes into account the acquisition of knowledge and experience in gender aspects of the public, social and labor spheres, in matters of economy, law, professional self-determination;

7. The personal aspect is directed at mastering the ways of self-development of the subject; understanding yourself as a subject of gender self-construction (*Danilenko. 2011. 21-23*).

Bern identifies such major components as a content component (knowledge of various issues of gender pedagogy and psychology), reflective component (personal attitude to different gender issues), and organizational component (ability to manage the process of gender socialization) (*Bern. 2004. 320*).

An analysis of the content, structure and components of gender competence has enabled us to determine the level of gender competency of future professionals in the social sphere (5th year students of the specialty "Social work" of Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University). In our study, we applied the following techniques:

1) Test "Determining the Level of Knowledge of Gender Terminology" H.P. Tsygankova (*Tsygankova. 2009. 76*), contains of 5 test questions with set of answers, which are focused on defining the real level of knowledge of gender terminology;

2) Questionnaire "Gender Stereotypes of Modern Student Youth" Z.V. Shevchenko (*Shevchenko. 2015*) aims to identify gender stereotypes inherent in the respondents among student youth, which contains 24 closed-ended questions, answers to which also provide an opportunity to examine the level of gender competence of future professionals.

3). Questionnaire "Formation of Gender Culture in Society" v. Kovalchuk (*Mishchik, Golovanova, Vasilyeva. 2006. 220*) focused on the study of the formation of the gender culture of society, the state of understanding of youth issues of gender equality, which contains 22 closed-ended questions with options for answers from 4 to 6.

4) Questionnaire "Methodology for diagnosing gender competence" O.I. Bondarchuk (*Bondarchuk. 2008. 318*) aims to identify level of knowledge of important aspects of gender problems of future professionals of social sphere, attitudes towards implementing a gender approach in an educational institution, based on solving

the situations suggested in the questionnaire (questions 18; 19; 20), can be judged to some extent on the operational component of gender competence. The questionnaire consists of 20 closed-ended questions with variants of answers.

Summarizing all the results we have investigated the level of gender competency of future social service providers and is presented in Picture 1.

Picture 1. The level of gender competency in future providers of social services

The analysis of the results of the pilot study shows that the average level of gender competency formation in future providers of social services exceeds, only 4 students have a sufficient level and 1 master has a low level of gender competence formation.

Conclusion. The results obtained indicate that the relevance of the investigated problem and the need to find a solution. First and foremost, the need is to develop future teachers with a range of skills and competences that would help them successfully complete their professional work in the field of social services. Based on that, we consider it necessary to introduce into the curriculum the training of future specialists in the social field of disciplines, the study of which will increase the level of gender competence of future social service providers, their willingness to use this competence in their further professional activity in the process of providing social services, ensure mastery of social services knowledge of analysis of gender problematic, and the application of this knowledge in practice, will help to form a modern perspective on issues, which concerning gender stereotypes of society.

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